

Supporting Information

Mechanoresponsive Behavior of a Polymer-Embedded Red-Light Emitting Rotaxane Mechanophore

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General Methods

All reagents and solvents were purchased from Tokyo Kasei, FUJIFILM Wako Pure Chemical Corporation, Kanto Chemical, or Merck. Unless otherwise noted, all reactions were carried out under nitrogen atmosphere. Flash silica gel column chromatography was performed with a Biotage Isolera Flash system using Biotage Flash Cartridges or SHOKO-scientific Purif-Pack-EX cartridges. Recycling preparative gel permeation chromatography (GPC) was conducted with a Japan Analytical Industry LaboACE. Inhibitor-free anhydrous tetrahydrofuran was used as solvent for the synthesis of polymers. Poly(tetrahydrofuran) ($M_n = 2,000$ g/mol) was dried *in vacuo* at 100 °C for 4 h before use. 4,4'-Methylenebis(phenylisocyanate) and 1,4-butanediol were distilled under vacuum and stored over molecular sieves at 4 °C and room temperature, respectively. ^1H NMR spectra were measured with a JEOL JNM-ECX 400 spectrometer and all chemical shifts are reported on the δ -scale in ppm relative to the signal of tetramethylsilane (TMS, at 0.00) even in in some cases referencing was based on residual solvent protons (THF at 1.72) as an internal standard. Proton-decoupled ^{13}C NMR spectra were performed with a JEOL JNM-ECX 400 spectrometer and all chemical shifts (δ) are quoted in ppm using residual solvent as the internal standard (CDCl_3 at 77.16). Coupling constants (J) are quoted in Hz and relative intensities are also shown. High resolution electrospray ionization (ESI) mass spectra were measured with a Thermo Scientific Exactive. Absorption spectra were recorded on a JASCO V-550. Steady-state fluorescence spectra of solutions were measured with a JASCO FP-6500 and the spectra were corrected for the detector nonlinearity. Steady-state fluorescence spectra of films during deformation experiments were monitored with an Ocean Optics QEPro-FL equipped with an LLS-385 LED light source and a Reflection/Backscattering Probe R400-7-UV-VIS; these spectra were not corrected. Time-resolved fluorescence measurements were carried out with a Hamamatsu Photonics Quantaaurus-Tau. Quantum efficiencies were measured with a Hamamatsu Photonics Quantaaurus-QY. Size-exclusion chromatography (SEC) experiments were carried out on an Agilent 1200 series HPLC system equipped with an Agilent PLgel mixed guard column (particle size = 5 μm) and two Agilent PLgel mixed-D columns (ID = 7.5 mm, L = 300 mm, particle size = 5 μm). Signals were monitored on a UV detector (Agilent 1200 series), an Optilab REX interferometric refractometer, and a miniDawn TREOS light scattering detector (Wyatt Technology Corp.). Samples were injected using THF as the eluent at 30 °C and a flow rate of 1.0 mL/min. Data analyses were conducted on Astra software (Wyatt Technology Corp.) and molecular weights were calculated based on narrow-molecular-weight polystyrene calibration (from 580 to 364,000 g/mol). Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) measurements were performed under N_2 on a Hitachi DSC7020 at heating and cooling rates of 10 °C/min. Thermogravimetric analyses (TGA) were conducted under air with a Mettler-Toledo Star^e system at a rate of 10 °C/min. Stress-strain measurements were carried out under ambient conditions with a SHIMADZU AGS-100NX equipped with a 100 N load cell at a strain rate of 300 mm/min. Dynamic mechanical analyses (DMA) were conducted under N_2 with a TA Instruments DMA Q800 at a heating rate of 3 °C/min, a frequency of 1 Hz, and an amplitude of 15 μm .

Sonomechanochemical Experimental Methods

Sonication Experiment: Sonication experiments were performed with a Branson Model 450 digital ultrasonic horn sonifier with a 13 mm tip. A PMX07R-20 refrigerated circulating cooling/heating bath from VWR containing 1/1 v/v water and ethylene glycol was used to maintain the sample temperature at 20 °C during sonication experiments. A solution containing the polymer in THF (Macron fine chemicals, ChromAR HPLC) with a concentration of 0.97 mg/mL was prepared and 20 mL were filled into a Suslick cell equipped with a gas outlet and a septum. The solution was degassed by purging with nitrogen for 15 min, cooled to 20 °C by immersion in the cooling bath, and submitted to sonication pulses of 0.5 s with an amplitude of 15% and a power density of 10.4 Wcm⁻² delayed by intermittent pauses of 1 s. Samples (350 µL) were taken after 0, 5, 10, 15, 20, 30, 40, 50, and 60 min with a syringe.

Fluorescence spectroscopy: Fluorescence spectroscopy was carried out with a Horiba Fluorolog 3 spectrometer with right angle illumination equipped with a 450 W Xenon light source for excitation and a FL-1030-UP photomultiplier as the detector. Spectra were recorded with a beam slit of 1.5 nm and an excitation wavelength of 550 nm. Fluorescence spectra were integrated between 560 and 750 nm to lower the impact of the low signal to noise ratio.

Size exclusion chromatography: Prior to SEC analysis, all samples were filtered with a 0.22 µm nylon syringe filter. Molecular weights were determined relative to polystyrene standards from 2,340 to 364,000 g/mol (Agilent Technologies) and were normalized between 0 and 17 min of elution time. The determined number-average molecular weight (M_n) at sonication time t were divided by the M_n at $t = 0$ min and plotted against sonication time.

Synthesis of Cyclic Compound 1 and Rotaxane 2

Conditions: Pd(PPh₃)₄, CuI, *i*-Pr₂NH, THF, r.t., 24 h.

Compound 4. A mixture of 2,6-diiodo-functionalized pentamethyl BODIPY **3**^{S1} (555 mg, 1.08 mmol), 3-(4-ethynylphenoxy)-1-propanol^{S2} (190 mg, 1.08 mmol), Pd(PPh₃)₄ (124 mg, 0.108 mmol), CuI (21 mg, 0.108 mmol) and *i*-Pr₂NH (5 mL) in THF (40 mL) was stirred under nitrogen atmosphere for 24 h at r.t. The reaction mixture was then poured into ethyl acetate (150 mL), the organic layer was separated off, washed with 5% aq. HCl (100 mL), saturated aq. NaHCO₃ (100 mL), and saturated aq. NaCl (100 mL), dried over MgSO₄ and filtered, and the solvent was evaporated. The crude product thus isolated was purified by flash column chromatography on silica gel (eluent: dichloromethane to dichloromethane/acetone = 9:1) to afford compound **4** (90.0 mg, 0.16 mmol, 15%) as a red solid.

¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃): δ = 1.65 (t, *J* = 5.2 Hz, 1H), 2.07 (quin, *J* = 6 Hz, 2H), 2.48 (s, 3H), 2.56 (s, 3H), 2.62 (s, 3H), 2.66 (s, 3H), 2.67 (s, 3H), 3.89 (q, *J* = 6 Hz, 2H), 4.16 (t, *J* = 6 Hz, 2H), 6.89 (d, *J* = 8.8 Hz, 2H), 7.45 (d, *J* = 8.8 Hz, 2H). MS(MALDI-TOF): *m/z*: 562.20 (calcd. [M]⁺ = 562.11).

Conditions: compound **4**, Pd(PPh₃)₄, CuI, *i*-Pr₂NH, THF, r.t., 24 h.

Compound 1. A mixture of compound **4** (90.3 mg, 0.160 mmol), compound **5**^{S3} (97.7 mg, 0.160 mmol), Pd(PPh₃)₄ (9.20 mg, 7.96 × 10⁻³ mmol), CuI (1.52 mg, 7.96 × 10⁻³ mmol) and *i*-Pr₂NH (5 mL) in THF (40 mL) was stirred under nitrogen atmosphere for 24 h at r.t. The reaction mixture was then poured into ethyl acetate (150 mL), the organic layer was separated off, washed with 5% aq. HCl (100 mL), saturated aq. NaHCO₃ (100 mL), and saturated aq. NaCl (100 mL), dried over MgSO₄ and filtered, and the solvent was evaporated. The crude product thus isolated was purified by flash column chromatography on silica gel (eluent: dichloromethane/acetone = 9:1 to dichloromethane/acetone = 4:1) and recycling GPC (eluent: chloroform) to afford compound **1** (30.0 mg, 0.0287 mmol, 18%) as a dark red solid.

¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃): δ = 1.68 (t, *J* = 5.2 Hz, 1H), 2.07 (quin, *J* = 6 Hz, 2H), 2.54 (s, 3H), 2.57 (s, 3H), 2.66 (s, 3H), 2.68 (s, 6H), 3.59–3.90 (m, 26H), 3.95–4.02 (m, 4H), 4.15 (t, *J* = 6 Hz, 2H), 4.18–4.23 (m, 4H), 6.40 (d, *J* = 8.8 Hz, 1H), 6.55 (dd, *J* = 3.2, 8.8 Hz, 1H), 6.72 (t, *J* = 7.2 Hz, 2H), 6.84–6.91 (m, 3H), 7.24–7.30 (m, 2H), 7.45 (d, *J* = 8.8 Hz,

2H), 7.84 (d, $J = 8.4$ Hz, 2H).

^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl_3): $\delta = 13.59, 13.66, 16.01, 16.03, 16.88, 32.01, 60.02, 65.53, 68.00, 68.02, 68.04, 68.56, 69.70, 69.80, 69.82, 70.74, 70.82, 70.93, 70.95, 70.99, 71.03, 80.41, 85.98, 93.08, 96.32, 105.62, 113.21, 113.53, 114.54, 114.66, 115.63, 115.82, 116.23, 116.47, 118.11, 125.20, 125.23, 126.71, 131.94, 131.98, 132.81, 141.50, 141.60, 142.24, 152.42, 153.44, 154.34, 154.37, 156.28, 156.63, 158.81$. HRMS (ESI): m/z : 1067.4657 (cacl. $[\text{M}]^+ = 1067.4653$).

Conditions: Compound 1, CuSO_4 , sodium ascorbate, CHCl_3 , H_2O , r.t., 24 h.

Compound 2. A mixture of sodium ascorbate (51.2 mg, 0.258 mmol), and copper(II) sulfate (20.6 mg, 0.129 mmol) in water (1 mL) was added to a solution of compound 1 (104 mg, 0.0861 mmol), $6^{\text{S}3}$ (90.0 mg, 0.0861 mmol), and $7^{\text{S}3}$ (64.6 mg, 0.0861 mmol) in chloroform (0.5 mL) and the mixture was vigorously stirred for 24 h at r.t. The suspension was poured into a mixture of water (100 mL) and chloroform (100 mL), before the organic layer was separated off, washed with saturated aq. NaCl solution (2×100 mL), dried over MgSO_4 and filtered, and the solvent was evaporated. The crude product thus obtained was purified by flash column chromatography on silica gel (eluent: dichloromethane/acetone = 4:1 to dichloromethane/acetone = 1:1) and recycling GPC (eluent: chloroform) to afford compound 2 (53.0 mg, 0.0176 mmol, 19%), as a dark purple solid.

^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3): $\delta = 1.28$ (s, 6H), 1.29 (s, 45H), 1.73 (s, 1H), 2.07 (quin, $J = 6.0$ Hz, 2H), 2.23 (t, $J = 6.4$ Hz, 1H), 2.45 (s, 3H), 2.57 (s, 3H), 2.60 (s, 3H), 2.70 (s, 3H), 2.71 (s, 3H), 3.57–4.18 (m, 82H), 4.54 (t, $J = 5.2$ Hz, 4H), 4.68 (s, 4H), 5.68 (d, $J = 3.2$ Hz, 1H), 5.80 (d, $J = 9.2$ Hz, 1H), 5.98 (dd, $J = 3.2, 8.2$ Hz, 1H), 6.10–6.16 (m, 2H), 6.66

(t, $J = 8.0$ Hz, 1H), 6.73 (t, $J = 8.4$ Hz, 1H), 6.76 (d, $J = 8.8$ Hz, 4H), 6.84 (d, $J = 8.8$ Hz, 2H), 6.90 (d, $J = 8.8$ Hz, 3H), 6.97 (d, $J = 8.4$ Hz, 1H), 7.03–7.08 (m, 16H), 7.20–7.24 (m, 10H), 7.46 (d, $J = 8.8$ Hz, 2H), 7.77 (s, 2H), 8.46 (s, 4H). ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl_3): $\delta = 13.46, 13.79, 15.88, 16.29, 17.17, 23.27, 31.79, 32.05, 34.39, 34.40, 38.50, 50.48, 60.20, 60.51, 63.04, 63.13, 64.65, 65.68, 67.15, 67.26, 67.29, 67.39, 67.52, 67.98, 68.76, 69.46, 69.77, 69.85, 70.02, 70.10, 70.45, 70.59, 70.66, 70.68, 70.70, 70.85, 70.94, 71.01, 71.12, 71.16, 71.23, 71.33, 71.37, 71.46, 80.28, 80.52, 85.48, 92.19, 96.60, 103.61, 103.66, 109.68, 111.44, 113.13, 113.21, 113.33, 114.25, 114.36, 114.67, 115.64, 116.04, 116.29, 116.68, 122.29, 123.77, 123.80, 123.92, 124.13, 124.22, 124.88, 124.95, 124.98, 125.20, 130.75, 130.81, 131.23, 131.84, 131.97, 132.13, 132.23, 132.30, 132.97, 139.66, 139.81, 141.66, 141.92, 142.39, 142.75, 144.10, 144.22, 145.09, 148.37, 148.54, 150.95, 151.74, 152.44, 153.20, 153.23, 156.47, 156.63, 156.72, 156.98, 158.97, 163.25$. HRMS (ESI): m/z : 1503.7761 (cacl. $[\text{M}+2\text{H}]^{2+} = 1503.7755$).

Polymer Synthesis

Synthesis of polyurethane 2-PU. Dibutyltin dilaurate (4 drops) was added to a stirred mixture of **2** (10 mg, 3.33×10^{-3} mmol), poly(tetrahydrofuran) ($M_n = 2,000$ g/mol, 3.00 g, 1.50 mmol), and 4,4'-methylenebis(phenylisocyanate) (1.26 g, 5.04 mmol) in THF (30 mL) and the mixture was stirred at r.t. for 3 h. A solution of 1,4-butanediol (297 mg, 3.30 mmol) in THF (10 mL) was then added and the reaction mixture was stirred at room temperature for an additional 24 h. EtOH (2 mL) was added to the reaction mixture and after stirring for another 30 min the reaction mixture was poured into EtOH (400 mL). The purple precipitate was collected by filtration, dissolved in THF (300 mL), the solution was filtrated through a cotton filter while approximately half of solvent evaporated, and the polymer was precipitated into hexane (300 mL). The precipitate was filtered off and dried *in vacuo* for 24 h at room temperature to afford **2-PU** as a purple rubbery solid (3.84 g, 84%, $M_n = 59$ kDa).

Preparation of Polyurethane Films

Preparation of 2-PU films. **2-PU** (300 mg) was dissolved in THF (10 mL) and the solution was divided between three round poly(tetrafluoroethylene) molds (32×3.5 mm). The molds were placed in a well-ventilated hood under an inverted funnel so that the evaporation rate was controlled. The solvent was evaporated overnight under ambient conditions and the resulting films were further dried *in vacuo* at room temperature overnight. The films thus obtained were smooth and transparent. The thickness of the films was 80–100 μm , as measured by a digital caliper.

Preparation of 1inPU and 2inPU films. A solution of compound **1** or **2** in THF (2 mL) was added to a THF solution (8 mL) of a reference polyurethane without any mechanophore, but of otherwise similar composition, which had been prepared in our previous study,^{S3} (ca. 0.3 g, $M_n = 115$ kDa) so that the concentration of compound **1** or **2** was same as that of the rotaxane units in **2-PU**. The mixture was divided between three round poly(tetrafluoroethylene) molds (32×3.5 mm) and the films were dried as described above. The films thus obtained are smooth and transparent. The thickness of the films was 80–100 μm , as measured by a digital caliper.

Preparation of swollen 2-PU films. The prepared **2-PU** film was swelled in solvents for 1 day at room temperature in glass vials. Then, the films were picked up and wicked with a paper tissue, then cut for experiments.

¹H NMR Spectra of Rotaxane 2

Figure S1. Partial ¹H NMR spectra of the BODIPY-based, cyclic luminophore **1** (top) and the corresponding rotaxane **2** (bottom). The abbreviations “ST”, “TA”, and “Npl” indicate signals ascribed to the stoppers, triazole, and quencher moieties, respectively. Both spectra were measured in CDCl₃ at 293 K.

¹H NMR Spectra of 2-PU

Figure S2. ¹H NMR spectrum of **2-PU** in THF-*d*₈. Signals are characterized as protons of the polyurethane chains. No signals ascribed to the rotaxane mechanophore are observed due to its low concentration. The spectrum was measured at 293 K.

Absorption and Photoluminescence Spectra of 2-PU in Solution

Figure S3. (a) Absorption and (b) photoluminescence spectra of **2** in chloroform (red) and **2-PU** in tetrahydrofuran (black). The concentration of **2** was 1.0×10^{-5} M. The concentration of **2-PU** (21 mg/mL) was tuned so that the absorbance caused by the mechanophore was comparable to that of **2**. The emission spectra were recorded with excitation light of 550 nm.

Thermal Properties of 2-PU

Figure S4. Thermogravimetric analyses (TGA) trace of **2-PU**. The TGA experiment was conducted under air at a heating rate of 10 °C/min.

Figure S5. Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) traces of **2-PU**. The heating and cooling rates were 10 °C/min.

Mechanical Properties of 2-PU

Figure S6. Dynamic mechanical analysis (DMA) traces of **2-PU**. The graph shows data from three different samples. The tests were conducted under N₂ at a heating rate of 3 °C/min, a frequency of 1 Hz, and an amplitude of 15 μm.

Figure S7. Stress-strain curves of (a) solution-cast **2-PU** films and (b) phenylacetonitrile swollen **2-PU** films. The graph shows data obtained from five different specimen. The experiments were conducted with a strain rate of 300 mm/min at room temperature.

Table S1. Mechanical data of the polyurethanes extracted from tensile tests.^{a)}

	Elongation at break (%)	Stress at break (MPa)	Young's modulus ^{b)} (MPa)
2-PU	1230 ± 180	43 ± 18	13 ± 3
Swollen 2-PU	1160 ± 460	4.6 ± 4	5.8 ± 2

^{a)}All data were extracted from the stress-strain curves shown in Figure S7 and represent averages of 5 measurements ± standard deviation. ^{b)}The Young's moduli were derived from the slopes of the stress-strain curves in the strain regime of 0.5–1.0%.

Emission Spectral Change of 2inPU upon Uniaxial Deformation

Figure S8. Photoluminescence spectra of a pristine **2inPU** film recorded upon uniaxial deformation to the strains indicated. The emission spectra were recorded with excitation light of 385 nm.

Emission Spectral Change of 1inPU upon Uniaxial Deformation

Figure S9. Photoluminescence spectra of a pristine **1inPU** film recorded upon (a) uniaxial deformation to the strains indicated and (b) releasing the stress so that the sample can relax from a strain of 600% to the strains indicated. The emission spectra were recorded with excitation light of 385 nm.

Swelling Tests of 2-PU films

Table S2. Results of swelling tests for **2-PU** films in various solvents

Swollen with strong quenching effect	Acetonitrile, Acetone, Chlorobenzene, Chloroform, Dichloromethane, Ethyl Acetate, Phenylacetoneitrile
Swollen with weak quenching effect	Tetrachloromethane, Toluene
Not swelled	Hexane, Methanol, Ethanol, Water

Sonomechanicochemical Experiments

Figure S10. (a) Size exclusion chromatography (SEC) traces of **2-PU** upon sonication for 1 h. The traces were normalized to the peak maximum of the chromatograms. (b) Changes of the photoluminescence spectra of the solutions upon sonication. (c) M_p/M_{p0} (black) and emission intensity (red) as a function of sonication time. M_p/M_{p0} is the ratio between the polymer's molar mass of the SEC trace after sonication for time t and the molar mass at $t = 0$ min. The emission intensity is based on the integration of the fluorescence spectra to reduce the impact of the limited signal to noise ratio. All sonication experiments were made with solutions of **2-PU** in THF.

Emission Spectra upon Releasing the Mechanical Stress

Figure S11. Photoluminescence spectra of **2-PU** acquired upon releasing the mechanical stress after stretching the film to a strain of 600%. The emission spectra were recorded with excitation light of 385 nm.

Emission Spectra of the Dried 2-PU Film

Figure S12. Photoluminescence spectra of a dried **2-PU** film (a) upon applying mechanical stress and (b) releasing mechanical stress. The film had been swelled in phenylacetonitrile for 1 day, then dried in vacuo for 1 day. The emission spectra were recorded with excitation light of 385 nm.

Mechanical Properties of the Dried 2-PU Film

Figure S13. Stress-strain curve of the dried **2-PU** after swelling with phenylacetonitrile for a day.

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Supporting Movies

Movie S1. Representative movie of the mechanoresponsive luminescent behavior upon cyclic stretching of the **2-PU** film.

Movie S2. Representative movie of the swelling effect and subsequent mechanoresponsive luminescent behavior upon cyclic stretching the **2-PU** film.

All movies were taken in the dark under excitation with 365 nm UV light.